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Girl YouTubers: Interaction, creation, educational content and emotions during COVID-19 confinement

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Abstract

The COVID-19 pandemic forced absolute confinement in Spain from March 15 to July 21, 2020. On the other side of the screen, YouTubers girls and boys, creators of specific content for their peers, took the opportunity to increase their productions. This research examines 73 creations made during the confinement period by six Spanish girls YouTubers categorized as influencers by the number of reproductions and followers of their channels through content analysis to evaluate the interactions, the content generated, and subjective aspects of projection of the emotional state of these minors. The